

THE PEDAGOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF INTEGRATING SPORTS MEDICINE APPROACHES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article presents information on the sports medicine approach to the educational process. The concept of sports medicine and its components, as well as their importance for students, are disclosed in detail.*

Keywords: *Sports medicine, concept, component, sports training, physical education, teacher, control, occupational hygiene, rehabilitation, healthy person, health, strengthening, diagnostics.*

It is known that the growing social significance of physical education and sports as an active means of supporting the comprehensive development of a growing young organism, its health and maintaining biological activity is an important health problem in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The sports medicine approach to the educational process is of great importance. Especially in the field of physical education, the pedagogical value of the sports medicine approach in improving the professional training of a teacher is incomparable. Pedagogy plays a major role in the development of a physical education teacher as a mature, qualified individual; it is safe to say that a qualified teacher is the most important factor in the effective entry of young specialists into professional activities [1].

Definitely, one of the approaches of sports medicine to the educational process is mainly the observation by doctors of the annual growth rates of physical development and functional state, as well as anthropometric indicators, which creates an idea of the influence of sports on the individual development of the body, allows students to make adjustments to the training process, helps with rest and nutrition [2,3].

It is fact that physical development is one of the leading criteria for assessing the health of the younger generation, its level is inextricably linked with environmental factors and most clearly changes in the lifestyle, which includes social, economic and reflects hygienic living conditions, as well as sports (Chubirko M.I. et al., 1997; Mokeeva M.M., Setko N.P., 2002; Zaitsev A.G., 2004; Kuchma V.R. et al., 2011) [4].

It is supported that sports medicine is a set of medical services related to sports, which are used to maintain the health of athletes, prevent injuries, rehabilitate and solve problems that may arise during sports.

Moreover, sports training and physical education are a social and pedagogical process in which the leading role is played by a coach and a teacher. However, the object of this process is a person with all the complexity of his psyche, body functions and relationships with the environment. In this regard, the effectiveness of the pedagogical process largely depends on the compatibility of the means and methods used with the health, functional capabilities, age and individual characteristics of each person. Any mistake by a trainer can have very bad consequences.

In addition, Sports medicine is a professional field, a type of activity focused on all types of medicine, which increases the effectiveness of the educational process in the field of physical education and sports, maintaining, strengthening, preventing and treating human health [5].

Also, sports medicine mainly includes the concepts of protecting and strengthening human health, medical rehabilitation of athletes, and occupational hygiene (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The basic concept of sports medicine.

The basic concepts of sports medicine include:

1. Injury prevention: development of special training and methods to prevent injuries to athletes.
2. Diagnostics: Use of modern diagnostic methods to identify sports injuries and diseases.
3. Rehabilitation: rehabilitation programs, physiotherapy and treatment of injured athletes.
4. Physical training: Improving the physical performance of athletes, increasing their performance.
5. Nutrition: Providing advice on proper nutrition and diets for athletes.
6. Psychological support: Monitoring the psychological state of athletes and providing psychological support if necessary.
7. Research and innovation: conducting new research in sports medicine, introducing innovative methods [6].

The concept of sports medicine includes the concept of occupational hygiene, which represents the conditions of a person's professional activity, his professional integration and factors that can affect the work environment. The concept of occupational hygiene includes medical, psychological and social aspects. The main elements included in this concept are:

1. Physical health: Physical condition of workers, occupational injuries, occupational diseases.
2. Psychological health. The impact of mental states such as anxiety, stress, depression on work productivity.
3. Social health: Relationships with the work community, social support and relationships.

To ensure occupational health, it is important to have top management of organizations, conduct specialized training of employees, conduct detailed medical examinations.

The concept of medical rehabilitation of athletes is a process of systematic recovery, restoration of health and return to sports activities of injured athletes. The main goal of this process is the maximum recovery of the athlete after injury, restoration of functional abilities and prevention of future injuries.

A team of professional specialists (physiotherapists, rehabilitation specialists, sports doctors) participates in this process. The effectiveness of rehabilitation is important for the health of the athlete and return to training [7].

There are several basic ways to protect and strengthen the health of a healthy person. These methods help to improve the physical, mental and social health of a person. In principle, important components are proper nutrition and an active lifestyle [8].

The implementation of these methods plays an important role in strengthening human health. Maintaining a healthy lifestyle is a responsible task for every person.

Therefore, the importance of sports medicine in the educational process is associated not only with its physical development, but also with intellectual, emotional and social development. Expansion of sports events in educational institutions, organization and holding of sports competitions among students is important for the overall development of students.

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